

Equilibrium and thermodynamic studies of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} adsorption onto *Artemisia vulgarise* (Paati) leaves

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Abstract : In the present study *Artemisia vulgarise* leaves (AVL) were used for removal of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} ions from aqueous solution. The plant *Artemisia vulgarise* is locally known as Paati. The investigation is carried out in a batch system with respect to adsorbent dose, pH, temperature, contact time, and initial metal ion concentration. The optimum adsorption conditions obtained were at contact time 75 min, pH 5, initial metal ion concentration 10 mg/L, temperature 15 °C and adsorbent dose 1.5 g for copper and 2 g for zinc and lead. The adsorption process is described by Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin models. Langmuir isotherm model provided a better fit with the experimental data than the Freundlich and Temkin isotherm. The results of the thermodynamic investigations indicated that the adsorption reactions were spontaneous ($\Delta G^\circ < 0$), feasible and exothermic ($\Delta H^\circ < 0$).

Keywords : Adsorption, heavy metals, *Artemisia vulgarise* leaves (AVL), Paati, isotherms, thermodynamic parameters.

Introduction

The discharge of industrial waste waters containing heavy metals is increasing due to rapid industrialization. Heavy metals are highly toxic even at low concentrations. They can accumulate in living organisms, causing several disorders and diseases¹. Copper, zinc and lead have been introduced in the environment from a variety of sources including storage battery², paints and pigments³, electronics⁴, fertilisers^{5,6} and electroplating^{7,8}. Excess of zinc in human body causes abdominal pain, lack of muscular coordination and acute renal failure while accumulation of copper causes liver damage, and chronic poisoning. The higher concentration of lead causes severe damage to the nervous system and affects the functioning of brain cells⁹. Various regulatory bodies have already set the maximum prescribed limits for the discharge of toxic heavy metals in the aquatic systems¹⁰. The permissible limits for industrial effluents discharge set by the World Health Organization (WHO)¹⁰ are 5–15 mg/L for Zn, 0.05–1.5 mg/L for Cu and 0.1 mg/L for Pb. Chemical precipitation¹¹, membrane filtration¹², ion exchange¹³ and carbon adsorption¹⁴ are few of the methods indicated in litera-

ture for the removal of heavy metals from water and waste water. However, these methods have their own disadvantages such as secondary pollution, high cost and high energy input. Among these methods biosorption is economically feasible method for removal of the heavy metals from the aqueous solution. Biosorption is the property of certain biomolecules to bind and concentrate selected ions or other molecules from aqueous solutions¹⁵. In recent years, many biological materials have appeared in the development of low cost adsorbent prepared from cheaper and easily available materials. Some of the recent adsorbents used are activated coconut shell¹⁶, mango peel waste¹⁷, sawdust¹⁸, orange barks¹⁹, rice husk²⁰, cocoa pod husk²¹, and plants dried²². *Artemisia vulgarise* leaves (AVL) is locally known as Paati. Though these plants can be seen in many parts of the country they are found abundantly in Kumaun hills. The *Artemisia vulgarise* (Paati) (AVL) is shown in Fig. 1.

The objective of the present work is to investigate the possibility of using activated AVL, as an alternative low-cost adsorbent for removal of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II}, ions from synthetic waste water.

Fig. 1. *Artemisia vulgaris* (Paati) leaves (AVL).

Results and discussion

Characterisation of adsorbent :

Fourier transforms infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy :

One of the important characteristics of a biosorbent is the surface functional groups present, which are largely characterized by the FTIR spectroscopy method. The spectrum gives information about the nature of possible interactions between the functional groups and the metal ions. The FTIR spectra of dried *Artemisia* leaf powder shows the presence of broad band at 3200 to 3400 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of hydroxyl (-OH), amine (-NH) and (-COOH) groups in biomass (Fig. 2). The band at 2900 cm^{-1} is assigned to aliphatic -C-H stretching vibration of -CH₃ and -CH₂ functional groups on the biomass surface. The bands at 1649 cm^{-1} is assigned to carboxyl

group. The peaks at 1374 and 1256 cm^{-1} represent -C-O-H bending, and -SO₃ stretching vibration respectively. This data confirmed that these functional groups could attract the positively charge objects such as heavy metal ions.

Effect of contact time :

Contact time is one of the most important parameter in biosorption processes. The effect of contact time on the biosorption of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} ions, performed on AVL is shown in Fig. 3. The curves indicate that the percentage removal of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} ions increases with increase in reaction time from 15 to 75 min. The percentage of metal removal is higher in the beginning due to availability of a larger surface area on the adsorbent for the adsorption of the metals.

Effect of adsorbent dosage :

In the present study the adsorbent dose is varied from 0.5 to 2.5 g to study the effect of the variation of adsorbent dose on adsorption. Biomass provides binding sites for the sorption of metal ions; its concentration strongly affects the sorption of metal ions from the solution²³. It was observed that percentage of metal ion removal is increased with increase in adsorbent dose from 0.5 to 2.0 g for copper, zinc and lead ions. The percentage of metal

Spectrum Graph

Fig. 2. FTIR spectrum of *Artemisia vulgaris* leaves.

Fig. 3. Effect of contact time on Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} adsorption [Experimental condition : Initial metal ions concentration = 10 mg/L, adsorbent dose = 1 g/100 ml, temperature = 22 °C, pH = 4.0 and agitating speed = 170 rpm].

ions removal does not show any remarkable change on further increase of the adsorbent dose (Fig. 4). Increase in adsorbent dose makes available more surface area for adsorption due to increase in active sites on the adsorbent resulting in easier penetration of metal ions to the sorption sites²⁴. However, at the same dose of adsorbent the adsorption capacity Q_e (Fig. 5) of copper, zinc and lead ions decreased. This is observed due to splitting effect of concentration gradient between sorbate and sorbent with increasing adsorbent dose.

Effect of pH :

The experimental data show that the percentage removal of the Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} ions increases with increasing pH from 1 to 5. After pH 5 the percentage removal decreases. In the case of zinc the percentage removal increases from pH 1 to 5 remain constant at pH 7 and the percentage removal decreases after pH 7. Handan *et al.*²⁵

Fig. 4. Effect of adsorbent dose on Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} adsorption [Experimental condition : Initial metal ions concentration = 10 mg/L, contact time = 30 min, temperature = 22 °C, pH = 4.0, agitating speed = 170 rpm].

Fig. 5. Effect of adsorbent dose on Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} adsorption capacity [Experimental condition : Initial metal ions concentration = 10 mg/L, contact time = 30 min, temperature = 22 °C, pH = 4.0, agitating speed = 170 rpm].

reported the optimum pH value of Cu at pH 5 and that is for Zn in between the pH 5 to 7. Here optimum pH is described as the pH at which any process (i.e. adsorption) is most effective under a given set of conditions.

Fig. 6 shows that biosorption efficiency is low when pH is less than 5 as the pH is lowered the overall surface charge on the biomass cells become positive and in this condition the protons compete with metal ions for ligands thereby decreases the interaction of metal ions with the cells²⁶. At higher pH (pH > 5) biosorption efficiency is decreased because of the formation of metal hydroxide and the ionized nature of the cell wall surface of the biomass²⁷.

Effect of initial Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions concentration :

The driving force to overcome the mass transfer re-

Fig. 6. Effect of pH on Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} adsorption [Experimental conditions : Initial metal ions concentration = 10 mg/L, adsorbent dose = 1 g/100 ml, contact time = 30 min, temperature = 22 °C, agitating speed = 170 rpm].

sistance between the aqueous and solid phases²⁸ is the initial concentration of metal ions in the solution. The percentage removal of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} ions is decreased with increasing initial metal ion concentration from 10 to 50 mg/L (Fig. 7). The reason is that at low initial metal ion concentration (10 mg/L), more surface area of the AVL is available for the adsorption, whereas with the increase in metal ions concentration (50 mg/L) the available surface area and binding sites becomes less for adsorption. However, at the same dose of adsorbent, the metal ions per unit of adsorbent Q_e (Fig. 8) have been increased with the increase of initial metal ion concentration.

Fig. 7. Effect of initial Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions concentration on adsorption [Experimental condition : Adsorbent dose = 1 g/100 ml, temperature = 22 °C, contact time = 30 min and pH = 4].

Fig. 8. Effect of initial Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions concentration on adsorption capacity [Experimental condition : Adsorbent dose = 1 g/100 ml, temperature = 22 °C, contact time = 30 min and pH=4].

Adsorption isotherm :

Isotherm gives information about adsorbent, which remove a pollutant or hazard metal from the solution at equilibrium. In the present study the data has been applied to Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm models.

Langmuir isotherm :

The Langmuir isotherm most widely used isotherm model for the biosorption process which assumes a surface with homogeneous binding sites, equivalent sorption energies, and no interaction between sorbed species²⁹. Eq. (1) represents the linear form of the Langmuir isotherm model.

$$\frac{C_e}{Q_e} = \frac{C_e}{Q_{max}} + \frac{1}{K_L Q_{max}} \quad (1)$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in mg/L. Q_e is the amount of metal adsorbed per specific amount of adsorbent (mg/g), K_L (L/mg) is the Langmuir constant related to the energy of adsorption and Q_{max} is maximum adsorption capacity (mg/g). Values of Langmuir parameters Q_{max} and K_L were calculated from the slope and intercept of linear plot of (C_e/Q_e) vs C_e shown in Fig. 9. The evaluated constants are given in Table 1.

The essential features of a Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in terms of a dimensionless constant separation factor “ R_L ” which is used to predict the adsorption system is favourable or unfavourable³¹ and is given as :

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + K_L C_i} \quad (2)$$

where C_i is the initial metal ion concentration in mg/L, K_L is the Langmuir equilibrium constant. The value of R_L indicated the type of Langmuir isotherm to be irreversible ($R_L = 0$), favourable ($0 < R_L < 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$) or unfavourable ($R_L > 1$). The value of R_L was found

Fig. 9. Langmuir isotherm for biosorption of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions onto AVL.

less than one in all the cases (Table 2). This confirms that the Langmuir isotherm model is favourable for adsorption of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} onto AVL.

Freundlich isotherm :

Freundlich isotherm is widely used to describe adsorption on a surface having heterogeneous energy distribution; the linear form of isotherm can be represented as³² :

$$\log Q_e = \log K_F + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (3)$$

where K_F is a constant related to the adsorption capacity and n is related to the adsorption intensity of the adsorbent. The constant K_F and value of $1/n$ can be determined from the linear plot of $\log Q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ (Fig. 10). The evaluated constants are given in Table 1.

Fig. 10. Freundlich isotherm for biosorption of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions onto AVL.

Table 1. Adsorption isotherm constants for adsorption of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} onto AVL

Metals	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Pb ^{II}
Langmuir parameters			
Q_{max} (mg/g)	0.88	0.46	0.86
K_L (L/mg)	0.21	1.33	0.42
R^2	0.98	0.99	0.99
Freundlich parameters			
K_F (mg/g) (L mg ⁻¹) ^{1/n}	0.56	0.62	0.63
n	3.24	11.32	4.34
R^2	0.61	0.30	0.33
Temkin parameters			
B (mg/g)	0.18	0.04	0.14
A	2.70	10.9×10^3	13.03
R^2	0.61	0.25	0.57

Temkin isotherm :

The Temkin isotherm model suggests that the adsorption energy decreases linearly with the surface coverage due to adsorbate-adsorbent interaction (Fig. 11). The eq. (4) is the linear form of the Temkin³³ isotherm

$$Q_e = B \ln A + B \ln C_e \quad (4)$$

where C_e is the concentration of the adsorbate at equilibrium mg/L, Q_e is the amount of metal adsorbed per specific amount of adsorbent (mg/g). $B = RT/b_T$, where R is the ideal gas constant (8.314 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) and T is the temperature in Kelvin, b_T is the Temkin isotherm constant, A is the equilibrium binding constant and B corresponds to the heat of sorption. The value of A and B are given in Table 1.

Fig. 11. Temkin isotherm for biosorption of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions onto AVL.

From Table 1 it is observed that the Langmuir isotherm is a good fit to the experimental equilibrium adsorption data than the Freundlich, and Temkin isotherm for Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} sorption according to the values of R^2 . It is observed from Table 1 that the Langmuir constant Q_{max} is 0.88, 0.46 and 0.86 and K_L is 0.21, 1.33 and 0.42 for Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}. The separation factor (R_L) values (Table 2) were found to be less than one and greater than zero indicating the favourable sorption of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} ions onto AVL. The Freundlich constant K_F indicates the sorption capacity of the sorbent and the value of K_F is 0.56, 0.62 and 0.63 for Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II}. It could be observed from the Table 1 that the regression coefficient was very low for Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II}; and the nature of adsorption is not heterogeneous which indicates that Freundlich isotherm is not obeyed, however, n is between 1 to 10 for Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} which is indication of

Table 2. R_L values based on the Langmuir isotherm

C_i (mg/L)	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Pb ^{II}
10	0.322	0.069	0.192
20	0.192	0.036	0.106
30	0.136	0.024	0.073
40	0.106	0.018	0.056
50	0.086	0.014	0.045

the favourable adsorption. The Temkin isotherm also not followed because of very low regression coefficient.

Biosorption thermodynamics :

Thermodynamic parameters such as enthalpy change ΔH° , free energy change ΔG° , and entropy change ΔS° used for thermodynamics behaviour of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} onto AVL and can be calculated from the following equations :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_D \quad (5)$$

where ΔG° is standard free energy change, R is the universal gas constant (8.314 J/mol K), T is the temperature in Kelvin. $K_D = C_{Ae}/C_e$ is the distribution coefficient³⁴, where C_e is the equilibrium concentration in solution in mg/L, and C_{Ae} is the equilibrium concentration on the sorbent in mg/L. Free energy change indicates the degree of spontaneity of the adsorption process and the higher negative value (-) a more energetically favourable adsorption^{35,36}.

The value of enthalpy ΔH° and entropy ΔS° were calculated from the slope and intercept of the plot $\ln K_D$ against $1/T$ as given in eq. (6). The value of free energy ΔG° , enthalpy ΔH° and entropy ΔS° are listed in Table 3.

$$\ln K_D = \frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R} - \frac{\Delta H^\circ}{RT} \quad (6)$$

From Table 3 it is clear that the reaction is spontaneous in nature. The negative values of ΔH° suggested the exothermic nature of the adsorption and the negative values of ΔG° indicated the spontaneous nature of the adsorption process, spontaneity decreases with an increase in temperature shows a decreases in feasibility of biosorption at higher temperature. The change of free energy for physisorption is between 0–20 kJ/mol; and the range for chemisorptions is 80–400 kJ/mol³⁷. These effects sug-

gested that the adsorption of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} ions onto AVL involves a physical process, which is usually associated with low adsorption heat³⁸, and the system does not gain energy from an external source. The negative ΔS° value suggests a decrease in the randomness at the solid/solution interface during the biosorption process³⁹ and also corresponds to a decrease in degree of freedom of the adsorbed species.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters for adsorption of Cu^{II}, Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} onto AVL

Heavy metals	T (K)	ΔG° (kJ/mol)	ΔH° (kJ/mol)	ΔS° (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Cu ^{II}	288	-5.23	-20.40	-54.64
	303	-3.18		
	318	-2.67		
	333	-2.33		
	348	-1.71		
Zn ^{II}	288	-3.33	-12.94	-34.42
	303	-2.19		
	318	-1.82		
	333	-1.41		
	348	-1.23		
Pb ^{II}	288	-6.38	-32.37	-91.70
	303	-3.94		
	318	-3.47		
	333	-1.37		
	348	-0.89		

Materials and methods :

Preparation of the adsorbate :

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions of 1000 mg/L concentration of lead nitrate; Pb(NO₃)₂, zinc sulphate; ZnSO₄·7H₂O and copper sulphate; CuSO₄·5H₂O were prepared. The working solutions were prepared by diluting the stock solutions using all glass double distilled water. The range in concentration of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions prepared from stock solution varied between 10 to 50 mg/L. The pH value of this solution is adjusted to 4 using 0.1 N NaOH and 0.1 N HCl solutions which is monitored by a digital pH meter (Model : Systronic 361).

Adsorbent : Preparation and collection :

Artemisia vulgarise leaves were collected from the fields around the fields of Kosi river of the district Almora,

Table 4. Batch adsorption experimental conditions

Experimental parameters	Metal ions	S (rpm)	Ms (g/100 ml)	t (min)	pH	C _i (mg/L)	Temp. (°C)
Effect of adsorbent mass, Ms (g)	Cu ^{II}	170	0.5–2.5	30	4	10	22
	Zn ^{II}	170	0.5–2.5	30	4	10	22
	Pb ^{II}	170	0.5–2.5	30	4	10	22
Effect of contact time, t (min)	Cu ^{II}	170	1.00	15–75	4	10	22
	Zn ^{II}	170	1.00	15–75	4	10	22
	Pb ^{II}	170	1.00	15–75	4	10	22
Effect of pH	Cu ^{II}	170	1.00	30	1–9	10	22
	Zn ^{II}	170	1.00	30	1–9	10	22
	Pb ^{II}	170	1.00	30	1–9	10	22
Effect of metal ion concentration, C _i (mg/L)	Cu ^{II}	170	1.00	30	4	10–50	22
	Zn ^{II}	170	1.00	30	4	10–50	22
Effect of temperature (°C)	Pb ^{II}	170	1.00	30	4	10–50	22
	Cu ^{II}	170	1.00	30	4	10	15–75
	Zn ^{II}	170	1.00	30	4	10	15–75
	Pb ^{II}	170	1.00	30	4	10	15–75

Uttarakhand, India. The collected leaves were thoroughly rinsed with double distilled water to remove dust and soluble materials. The biomass was further dried at room temperature and then kept in hot air oven (Popular Trad-ers S.N.-1680) for 24 h at 70 °C; it was grinded to a fine powder using grinder-mixer then this powdered mass was treated with 0.1 N HNO₃ at room temperature for 24 h, filtered, washed with double distilled water and dried in hot air oven at 70 °C for 2 days and sieved (240 bss) at 63 micron. The treated biomass was then kept in air tight bottle. The surface functional groups of the activated bio-mass were identified by Fourier transforms infrared spec-troscopy using FTIR Model no. 1760 X, Perkin-Elmer USA.

Adsorption experiments :

The batch sorption experiments were carried out with 250 ml conical flask using 100 ml of working solution with a concentration of 10 mg/L. The experimental con-ditions applied to examine the effect of adsorbent dose, contact time, pH, temperature and initial metal ion con-centration in adsorption of metal ions on adsorbent was shown in Table 4. The AVL was separated from the me-dium with the help of Whatman (No. 42) filter paper. In a filtrate the concentration of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} metal ions was measured by Atomic Adsorption Spectrophotometer

AAS (Optima 4300 DV ICP, Perkin-Elmer, Boston, MA). The percentage removal of metal ion (Pb, Cu or Zn) is calculated using the following formula :

$$\text{Removal (\%)} = \frac{(C_i - C_e)}{C_i} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

where C_i is initial metal ion concentration (mg/L) and C_e is the equilibrium metal ion concentration (mg/L).

Conclusion

The AVL biomass was used for the removal of cop-per, zinc and lead from the synthetic waste water. The maximum removal was found at pH 5.0. At pH greater than 5 the metal ions get precipitated due to the formation of metal hydroxides. The adsorption decreases with in-creasing the initial metal ion concentration and adsorption capacity increases with increasing metal ion concentra-tion. Adsorption of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions on AVL in-creases with increasing the adsorbent dosage. Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin adsorption models were used with the experimental data. These experimental data fitted very well to the Langmuir isotherm model. Thermodynamic analysis suggests that the removal of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} from synthetic waste water onto AVL is a spontaneous and exothermic in nature.

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